

Growing and Sustaining the PlasmaPy Software Ecosystem¹

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Project Summary

Overview

PlasmaPy is an open source Python package containing core functionality for plasma science. Overall, the mission of the PlasmaPy project is to grow a fully open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education: a collection of scientific software packages that are developed together, work together, and co-evolve in the same environment. The project team will expand PlasmaPy to include additional, powerful tools for analyzing data from the most important and widely used diagnostics for both high energy density physics and magnetized laboratory plasma experiments. The team will expand functionality needed by the heliophysics community to analyze and understand measurements of plasma in the solar wind, Earth's magnetosphere, and coronal mass ejections. The team will develop software infrastructure in PlasmaPy to make laboratory plasma data sets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) and improve the plasma science data environment. Because few members of the plasma community have much experience making open source contributions, the project team will (1) organize three summer schools for students and scientists to learn how to contribute to an open source software project like PlasmaPy, (2) forge a partnership between PlasmaPy and the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE); and (3) provide numerous training opportunities for undergraduate, postbaccalaureate, and graduate students. The proposed code development and data environment improvements, focused on three topical areas and in collaboration with researchers in these fields, will increase adoption of PlasmaPy while improving scientific productivity through coordinated software development and metadata standardization. The proposed training efforts will tackle research software engineering (RSE) skills gaps within the community, and significantly grow the contributor pool for PlasmaPy. Both of these proposed efforts will lead to long-term sustainability of the PlasmaPy Project software ecosystem and maximize its impact on plasma science innovation and education.

Intellectual Merit

This project team will enhance PlasmaPy with functionality for the most important diagnostics in both magnetized laboratory plasma experiments and high energy density physics. This functionality will facilitate innovation by enabling researchers to interpret

¹ This collaborative research proposal was submitted to the *Framework Implementations* track of the Cyberinfrastructure for Sustained Scientific Innovation (CSSI) program of the National Science Foundation on December 2, 2024.

diagnostic data sets and investigate fundamental science questions related to plasma turbulence, magnetic reconnection, collisionless shocks, wave interactions, coronal heating, instabilities, and particle acceleration. By providing the plasma community with reliable and interoperable open source software, this project will lay a foundation for open and reproducible plasma science. This project will shorten the time and difficulty needed by researchers to achieve scientific understanding and innovation by making it easier to compare results from different experiments, perform cross-facility and cross-disciplinary studies, and develop new experimental facilities. By improving PlasmaPy interoperability in the Python ecosystem for heliophysics, this project will reduce the effort needed by scientists to analyze space plasma data. Enhancements to the PlasmaPy software ecosystem will be made in close collaborations with MagNetUS, the Python in Heliophysics Community, and members of the high energy density physics community.

Broader Impacts

This project will grow and sustain the next generation of RSEs and computational physicists in plasma science via tutorials, summer schools, year-long training opportunities, and through supporting two CRANE online course cycles for undergraduate students. By actively recruiting participants from diverse backgrounds, including underrepresented groups and Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs), this project will broaden participation and foster inclusivity in the plasma community. Growing the PlasmaPy ecosystem allows the plasma community to pool resources and reduce the cost required for building new plasma experiments, especially at small and under-resourced institutions. This project will broaden access to plasma science and reduce barriers to entry by providing free access to well-documented and well-tested software. The project team will continue to enhance PlasmaPy's documentation and promote it as a freely available educational resource for plasma science, including notebooks that use PlasmaPy to introduce plasma concepts along with concrete examples. This effort will provide functionality beneficial for a wide variety of fields, including laboratory plasma physics, high energy density physics, solar physics, space plasma physics, astrophysics, low temperature plasma science, and fusion energy sciences.

Project Description

1. Introduction

Software is crucial to all areas of plasma science. Laboratory plasma physicists utilize software when calibrating plasma diagnostics and analyzing experimental data. Space scientists use software to interpret in situ observations of space plasma. Computational plasma scientists use software to simulate the behavior of laboratory, heliospheric, and astrophysical plasmas. Theoretical plasma physicists use software to derive models and visualize results. Educators and students use software to interactively explore plasma phenomena and understand plasma concepts.

Despite its importance, plasma science has historically lacked a culture where software was openly developed and shared as a community. Plasma code development has generally been directed toward a particular purpose for a research publication, which makes the resulting code harder to reuse or repurpose for different applications. Research groups have typically developed analysis codes in-house as needed, so there has been little emphasis on interoperability. Submitting journal articles has generally been prioritized over documentation and user experience. Codes have often lacked a testing framework, which can make users reluctant to make changes for fear of breaking something somewhere else in the code. These factors have limited scientific innovation and increased the difficulty of starting research, reproducing scientific results, and collaborating within or across disciplines.

PlasmaPy began in 2017 as a grassroots effort by students and scientists who were motivated to fundamentally change how the plasma community develops software. Following inspiration from the Astropy and SunPy communities (Astropy Collaboration 2022; SunPy Community 2023), we invited the community to create a Python package for plasma physics. After making two early development releases, we received a five-year collaborative NSF CSSI Framework award in 2019 that enabled us to transform PlasmaPy into a mature, well-established package with 147 contributors. We are proposing to renew this award. PlasmaPy contains a wide range of functionality, such as calculation of plasma parameters, plasma wave dispersion relationships, particle tracking, analyzing and synthesizing data from plasma diagnostics, and representing plasma configurations and equilibria. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of plasma science,¹ **PlasmaPy is now used in heliophysics, high energy density physics (HEDP), laboratory plasma physics, astrophysics, low temperature plasma science, and fusion energy sciences.** The need for PlasmaPy has been recognized in multiple high-level community reports for plasma science,² fusion energy sciences,^{3,4} and HEDP.⁵

The mission of the PlasmaPy project is to grow a fully open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education. A software ecosystem is a collection of interoperable software packages that are developed and co-evolve in the same environment. A software ecosystem includes code, documentation, tests, educational resources, and community. PlasmaPy itself contains functionality that is broadly needed by plasma scientists across subdisciplines. The PlasmaPy ecosystem includes established packages like `fiasco` for providing access to atomic data (Barnes et al. 2024) and

¹This proposal is most relevant to the MPS/PHY, GEO/AGS, and MPS/AST divisions of NSF.

²The Plasma 2020 decadal review (NASEM 2021) recommends: “Funding agencies, and in particular DOE and NSF, should support mechanisms for making computational plasma software more widely accessible to noncomputing experts, and to transition current codes to new computing architectures.”

³The final report of the American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP) Community Planning Process includes community consensus recommendations to: “Establish a network program to foster the development of an open source, programming ecosystem for plasma physics and advance computational plasma science” and “Support improvements to the accessibility, interoperability, reproducibility, and user-friendliness of FES-funded codes and their outputs” (APS DPP CPP 2020).

⁴FESAC (2020) recommends to “Support networks to coordinate research and broaden access to state-of-the-art facilities, diagnostics, and computational tools.”

⁵LaserNetUS (2023) states that “Common analysis codes should be open source and written for easy sharing throughout the community” and “Repeatable, open-source-analysis routines could be adapted into an existing code base, such as PlasmaPy.”

`bapsflib` (Everson et al. 2024) for providing access to data from the Basic Plasma Science Facility (BaPSF), and forthcoming packages like `wiPPLPy` (for the Wisconsin Plasma Physics Laboratory; WiPPL) and `pygasus3` (for the Pegasus III tokamak at the University of Wisconsin). As a core package of the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC), PlasmaPy is included in the Python ecosystems for astronomy and heliophysics. PlasmaPy is used with PyHC packages such as SpacePy, pySPEDAS, and Kamodo, including as a participant in the first executable paper in heliophysics (Poison et al. 2023).

The PlasmaPy project has developed multiple suites of functionality. We have found that adoption of functionality is more widespread when developed in partnership with a particular subgroup from the plasma community. The most successful example of this was with members of the HEDP community. Partnering with collaborator P. Heuer enabled PlasmaPy's Thomson scattering analysis package to become PlasmaPy's most widely used diagnostic functionality (Foo et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2023, Pilgram et al. 2024, Pokornik et al. 2024, Eisenbach et al. 2025). **We therefore propose to develop diagnostic and analysis functionality for three subfields of plasma science: experimental magnetized plasma research, HEDP, and heliophysics.** We will develop these capabilities in close coordination with members of these communities. In §4.1, we propose to develop software capabilities needed to analyze data from the most important diagnostics for magnetized plasma experiments in partnership with the MagNetUS community.⁶ In §4.2, we propose to add functionality to analyze the most important diagnostics in experimental HEDP research, in partnership with Co-PI D. Schaeffer, Collaborator C. Kuranz, and Dr. Heuer. In §4.3, we propose to partner with PyHC to add functionality needed by the solar and space physics communities. Through these partnerships, we will grow the user and contributor bases of PlasmaPy to improve software sustainability, and enable innovation by providing diagnostic analysis tools that underpin a wide range of scientific research. Fully developing functionality for these particular areas will have the broadest impact and applicability throughout plasma science, which will in turn increase adoption of PlasmaPy and secure long-term software sustainability.

During the past five years, the prime challenge faced by the PlasmaPy project has been that **not many members of the plasma community have experience contributing to an open source package.** Throughout the first grant period, we encountered significant enthusiasm from members of the community interested in contributing to PlasmaPy. Because the essential research software engineering skills like version control are rarely covered in plasma coursework, prospective contributors have typically required substantial aid from core maintainers to make their contributions to PlasmaPy. We held the inaugural PlasmaPy Summer School in 2024 to provide an opportunity for members of the plasma community to learn how to use and contribute to an open source package like PlasmaPy.

To fully realize the potential of PlasmaPy, we propose in §5 to undertake a series of educational efforts to train the next generation of research software engineers (RSEs) in plasma science and ensure the long-term growth and sustainability of PlasmaPy. We will hold three biannual PlasmaPy Summer Schools for a wide audience of plasma students and scientists to learn how to use and contribute to an open source project like PlasmaPy. We will provide numerous 12-month research & training opportunities for undergraduates, postbaccalaureates, and predoctoral fellows (predocs) to work directly with a core contributor to add important new functionality to PlasmaPy. Finally, we will forge a partnership with the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE) to provide a pathway for undergraduates from historically marginalized groups to become computational physicists and RSEs.

2. PlasmaPy: Overview and Current Status

PlasmaPy is a community-driven open source Python package for plasma research and education (PlasmaPy Community 2024). PlasmaPy provides core functionality needed by plasma students and scientists across subdisciplines. It serves as a platform for the plasma community to collaboratively develop and share needed research software functionality. Development of PlasmaPy prioritizes best practices for scientific computing (Wilson et al. 2014) and writing clean scientific software (Murphy

⁶MagNetUS is a coalition of user facilities for experimental magnetized plasma research, including BaPSF, WiPPL, the Magnetized Plasma Research Facility (MPRL) at Auburn University, the DIII-D tokamak, PHASMA at West Virginia University, and the NRL Space Physics Simulation Chamber.

2023a–b). PlasmaPy has evolved into a robust toolkit that is addressing the software infrastructure needs of plasma science. PlasmaPy’s capabilities range from calculating plasma parameters and transport coefficients to creating synthetic diagnostics for high energy density (HED) plasma. Most of PlasmaPy’s functionality incorporates and is interoperable with `astropy.units`. PlasmaPy’s subpackages and breadth of capabilities are summarized in the following table. Applications of PlasmaPy are highlighted in Figs. 1–3 and §3.1.

Subpackage	Description
<code>particles</code>	Provides functional and object-oriented access to particle data, underpinning most of PlasmaPy. Includes the <code>Particle</code> and <code>CustomParticle</code> classes to represent single particles, the <code>ParticleList</code> class to represent a collection of particles, and classes to represent the ionization state for multiple elements in a plasma.
<code>formulary</code>	Enables calculation of a wide variety of fundamental plasma parameters, collision frequencies, and plasma transport coefficients. Draws from and builds upon the widely used NRL Plasma Formulary (Beresnyak 2023).
<code>dispersion</code>	Provides analytical and numerical solutions to the dispersion relations in different regimes that are fundamental to the study of plasma waves and describe how waves propagate at different frequencies and angles from the magnetic field.
<code>analysis</code>	Contains analysis techniques and focused tools applicable to experimental or simulation data, such as for swept Langmuir probe analysis, excess statistics time series analysis, and finding null points in a 3D magnetic field for reconnection studies.
<code>diagnostics</code>	Contains integrated analysis tools for working with real or synthetic data from plasma diagnostics, such as for synthetic charged particle radiography, optical Thomson scattering, and Langmuir probe analysis.
<code>plasma</code>	Contains base classes for representing plasma, such as on a 3D grid.
<code>simulation</code>	Contains the <code>ParticleTracker</code> class and supporting functionality for simulations.
<code>utils</code>	Contains utility functionality used throughout PlasmaPy, such as Python decorators that are used to validate the inputs to most <code>formulary</code> functions.

PlasmaPy’s documentation describes how to use a function along with the underlying physics. Each function in PlasmaPy has a docstring that follows the `numpydoc` standard. The docstrings include a description of what each function does, parameters to be supplied to it, return types, and examples showing how it can be used. Docstrings for functions related to plasma concepts include educational notes on the underlying physics. Subpackages such as `plasmapy.particles` also have comprehensive narrative documentation. The gallery of 31 example notebooks introduces how to use PlasmaPy along with associated plasma concepts. PlasmaPy’s documentation is written in `reStructuredText`, built using Sphinx, hosted on Read the Docs, and tested for each pull request.

PlasmaPy’s documentation has an extensive contributor guide. This guide describes getting ready to contribute, the code contribution workflow, coding best practices, writing/running tests, writing/building documentation, and ways to contribute beyond code. This guide has been used to start packages like `WIPPLPy`, and excerpts from it have been incorporated into the `pyOpenSci` packaging guide.

PlasmaPy has an extensive test suite to ensure reliability and maintainability. Tests help us find and fix bugs, prevent old bugs from recurring, and provide confidence that code is behaving as expected. Tests let us change code with confidence that we are not unknowingly introducing bugs elsewhere in the program. PlasmaPy uses `pytest` as its primary test runner, while using the Nox automation tool to ensure that tests are run consistently across platforms. Tests are run for all supported versions of Python and for multiple operating systems. Doctests ensure that docstring examples are correct. Approximately 95% of lines of code in PlasmaPy are covered by at least one of the 4390 tests. PlasmaPy’s continuous integration suite includes static type checking with `mypy` along with linters and code quality checks.

Fig. 1: This figure from Heuer et al. (2022) compares experimental radiographs with simulated radiographs created using PlasmaPy, highlighting PlasmaPy's capability of allowing users to validate their simulated data results. The top row proton radiographs were created from three different cylindrical implosion experiments conducted at the OMEGA Laser System, and the bottom row synthetic radiographs were generated by supplying electromagnetic fields from 3D radiation hydrodynamics simulations into PlasmaPy's charged particle radiography module.

Fig. 2. A 2D map by Pilgram et al. (2024) of electron density (top) and electron temperature (bottom, mirrored) during a laser-driven shock in an HEDP experiment. These quantities were found using PlasmaPy's Thomson scattering module, and then used to show that the magnetic field was generated via the Biermann battery (a proposed mechanism for the origin of seed magnetic fields in the early universe).

Fig. 3. The temperature ratio between α particles and protons in the solar wind at 1 au. The blue curve is the prediction from applying PlasmaPy's `collisional_analysis` module to *Parker Solar Probe* data. The red-dashed curve shows observations by the *Wind* spacecraft. The similarity shows that preferential heating occurs 0.27 au from the Sun (Johnson et al. 2023).

3. Results from Prior NSF Support

Several members of our team are supported by an NSF CSSI award entitled: *Collaborative Research: Frameworks: An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics*.⁷ Derek Schaeffer is PI of an award entitled *Laboratory Studies of Laser-Driven, Ion-Scale Mini-Magnetospheres on the LAPD*.⁸ Prior to forming as a non-profit, CRANE activities were funded by the award *CAREER: The Bryn Mawr Plasma Laboratory---A liberal-Arts Centered Facility for Basic Plasma Research and Plasma Science Education*.⁹

3.1. Intellectual merit from prior NSF support

When our original CSSI award began, PlasmaPy was a fledgling package with only two preliminary releases made over a year apart. Since then, we have made 14 feature releases and reduced the time between releases to ~3 months. We have merged 1303 pull requests since the start of the award and have had 147 unique contributors. PlasmaPy's GitHub repository has been starred 575 times and forked 338 times, indicating broad community interest. Releases of PlasmaPy are on the Python Package Index (PyPI), conda-forge, GitHub, and on Zenodo (PlasmaPy Community 2024). Total PyPI downloads of PlasmaPy increased by 88% between years 4 and 5 (Fig. 4). Although this award coincided with a global pandemic, we grew PlasmaPy from a side project into a well-known effort that is being adopted across the plasma community.

PlasmaPy is used in heliophysics

(Barnes et al. 2019; DuPont et al. 2020; Qudsi 2021; Maruca et al. 2021; Jara-Almonte et al. 2022; Raymond et al. 2022; Krämer et al. 2023; Polson et al. 2023; Johnson et al. 2023, 2024; Johnson 2024), **high energy density physics** (HEDP; Pliatskas Stylianidis et al. 2019, Heuer et al. 2022, Davies et al. 2022, Simpson et al. 2023, Foo et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2023, Chen et al. 2024, Pokornik et al. 2024, Pilgram et al. 2024, Daneshmand et al. 2024, Rigon et al. 2024, Eisenbach et al. 2025), **laboratory plasma physics** (A. Murphy et al. 2023, L. Murphy 2024, Creamer 2024), **astrophysics** (Feinstein et al. 2022), **low temperature plasmas** (Jubin et al. 2024), and **fusion energy sciences** (Kennedy & Salmonson 2023).

Fig 4. Monthly downloads of PlasmaPy from PyPI.

This award has enabled extensive improvements to PlasmaPy — both by ourselves and in partnership with the plasma community. We defined the top-level package infrastructure (Everson et al. 2019) and reorganized the `formulary` into its modern form. Undergraduate and graduate students at U. Delaware created `plasmapy.dispersion`, which contains the most commonly used dispersion relations for plasma waves (Alfvén 1942, Stringer 1963, Hollweg 1999, Bellan 2012). We extended `plasmapy.particles` to contain the `CustomParticle` and `ParticleList` classes, and adapted the ubiquitous `@particle_input` decorator to make the `formulary` interoperable with the new objects. We made and supported numerous additions to `analysis` and `diagnostics`, including Langmuir analysis, a magnetic null point finder and classifier, excess statistics time series analysis, charged particle radiography, and Thomson scattering. We overhauled the contributor guide to improve sustainability. We modernized packaging and the continuous integration infrastructure while enabling static type checking. In the next three paragraphs, we highlight examples of how PlasmaPy has enabled scientific innovation.

We worked with Dr. Heuer to add a module in `plasmapy.diagnostics` for **charged particle radiography** — a technique used to diagnose the structure of electric and magnetic fields in high energy density plasmas (Heuer et al. 2022, Schaeffer et al. 2023). The area of interest is positioned between a bright source of protons and a detector. Electromagnetic fields deflect particles as they pass through the

⁷This collaborative project includes NSF awards 1931388 to the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (PI: N. Murphy, \$1,439,530), 1931429 to UCLA (PI: S. Vincena, \$539,583), 1931393 to Bryn Mawr College (PI: D. Schaffner, \$187,240), and 1931435 to U. Delaware (PI: B. Maruca, \$273,452) with a period of performance from 2019-10-01 to 2025-09-30 (with a 1 year no-cost extension).

⁸NSF award 2320946 to UCLA is for \$499,999 from 2023-04-01 to 2025-11-30.

⁹NSF award 1846943 to Bryn Mawr College is for \$564,631 from 2019-08-15 to 2025-07-31.

plasma, producing patterns on the detector. PlasmaPy's `charged_particle_radiography` module can be provided with electromagnetic fields defined on a 3D grid to produce a synthetic radiograph. By using PlasmaPy to create synthetic radiographs from a numerical simulation and comparing them to experimental radiographs, researchers can validate the simulation and ascertain whether the physical model is complete or missing important effects. For example, Heuer et al. (2022) found that their simulations were able to reproduce large-scale structures but were missing small-scale features (Fig. 1).

Thomson scattering is a plasma diagnostic that provides reliable localized measurements of the density, temperature, and energy distribution function of electrons (Finch et al. 2021). In this technique, a laser beam induces elastic interactions between photons and free electrons that scatter light. With Dr. Heuer, we added the `thomson` module to `plasmapy.diagnostics` to perform fits of the Thomson scattered power spectrum to provide localized electron temperature and density. Pilgram et al. (2024) used this module to create a 2D map of the electron density and temperature during a laser-driven blast wave in an experiment (Fig. 2). Their results demonstrate that the measured magnetic field was created via the Biermann battery — a mechanism proposed as the origin of magnetic fields in the early universe.

PlasmaPy is used to address key questions in heliophysics such as: how is the solar wind heated? Different ion species are commonly observed to have different temperatures in the weakly collisional solar wind. For example, ${}^4\text{He}^{2+}$ ions (α particles) often have a higher temperature than protons. Ion temperature ratios provide important constraints on plasma heating mechanisms in the solar wind. This award enabled recent U. Delaware graduate student E. Johnson to create PlasmaPy's `collisional_analysis` module from his thesis research (Johnson 2024). Dr. Johnson added functionality to model the evolution of ion temperature ratios of a plasma in transit due to particle collisions. By applying this functionality to observations from *Parker Solar Probe* and comparing it to observations from *Wind*, Dr. Johnson found the important constraint that most preferential heating between α particles and protons occurs within 0.27 au of the Sun (Fig. 3; Johnson et al. 2024).

Prior to forming as a non-profit organization in 2024, CRANE was funded via an NSF CAREER supplement to conduct two cycles of their 16-week free online Python course in 2023 and 2024. The two cycles served 180 total students, 43 of whom received a stipend for their participation. Stipends were also awarded to instructors and TAs. The curriculum covered the following topics: Part 1: Intro to Python, Part 2: Numerical Methods, and Part 3: Advanced Algorithm Tracks for which students could pick among Signal and Image Processing, Astronomy and Data Analysis, Monte Carlo, or Particle-In-Cell (PIC) methods. Some CRANE students were provided with one-on-one mentorship with CRANE leads, which often continued long after the cycle ended. In post-program survey evaluations, all students felt that they learned to code in a supportive environment, and almost all felt comfortable teaching introductory Python to a peer and that they were provided an opportunity to develop their research skills.

Prof. Schaeffer developed a novel high-repetition-rate platform at UCLA for studying ion-scale magnetospheres that combined the magnetized plasma of the LAPD and high-powered laser driver from the Phoenix Laser Laboratory with a pulsed dipole magnet. Initial experiments demonstrated the creation of a laser-driven ion-scale magnetosphere (Schaeffer et al. 2022), which were well-matched by comprehensive 2D PIC simulations (Cruz et al. 2022). Follow-on numerical studies identified the mechanisms by which the laser-driven plasma couples energy into the background plasma (Cruz et al. 2023), a critical component for generating the laboratory magnetosphere. Recent experiments further demonstrated driven magnetic reconnection and the first 3D volumetric measurements of magnetic and electric fields in an ion-scale magnetosphere using the same platform (Rovige et al. 2024).

3.2. Broader impacts from prior NSF support

PlasmaPy has consistently been connected to the larger plasma community and strives for broader engagement. At the 2020 APS-DPP meeting, we organized a mini-conference called Growing an Open Source Software Ecosystem for Plasma Science. This mini-conference had talks on PlasmaPy, software citation, open hardware, metadata standards, and plasma software. We led the organization of Plasma Hack Week in 2021 and 2022, which had a peak attendance of ~100 people each year. Plasma Hack Weeks included structured tutorials on how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy (now available on PlasmaPy's YouTube channel), as well as unstructured hack sessions as opportunities to put the lessons

into practice. The hack sessions in 2022 were an opportunity for participants to contribute to a “hack formulary” akin to `plasmapy.formulary`. Some functions added to the hack formulary were later incorporated into PlasmaPy. We hold weekly virtual office hours so that the community can engage with us directly. The highest attendance has been from students. At APS DPP meetings from 2022–2024, we hosted in-person exhibitor booths that allowed us to engage with ~100 attendees each year.

We led multiple tutorials annually, covering various forums, topics, and audiences. Dr. Murphy and Dr. Heuer delivered PlasmaPy tutorials at the Summer Undergraduate Laboratory Internship (SULI) Introduction to Fusion Energy and Plasma Physics Course from 2021–2024, with videos available on the SULI website. Dr. Murphy led tutorials at the PyHC summer schools in 2022 and 2024, and at multiple meetings in 2022–2024. Dr. Murphy gave Python tutorials for solar REU students at SAO and presented on *Making Plasma Science Open* at the Computational Physics School for Fusion Research at MIT from 2021–2024 (Murphy 2023c). Dr. Murphy frequently presented on *Writing Clean Scientific Software*, including a widely attended Exascale Computing Project webinar (Murphy 2023a). The slides from this presentation (Murphy 2023b) have garnered ~8000 views and ~1300 downloads.

The final major event of the grant cycle was a fully in-person **PlasmaPy Summer School** held at Bryn Mawr College in July 2024. The primary goal of the school was to train a potential new group of PlasmaPy contributors. We solicited applications from the plasma community and chose 25 participants from 82 applications. Each participant was provided full travel funding through the award. The attendees were chosen based on potential for contribution to the PlasmaPy project, and ranged from undergraduates to tenured faculty. The school incorporated lessons from previous Hack Weeks and tutorials on effective RSE education. Lessons covered submitting pull requests, coding best practices, writing tests, and how to use various PlasmaPy modules. The school included a discussion on psychological safety during code review as well as multiple participant-driven unconference sessions.

This award enabled us to play an important and ongoing role in workforce development. We have advised multiple students, including one undergraduate and two graduate students at U. Delaware, two undergraduate interns at SAO, five students at Bryn Mawr College, and one Plasma and Fusion Undergraduate Research Opportunities (PFURO) intern. We regularly create GitHub issues and label them as “good first issue” along with labels describing difficulty levels. These issues are often used by newcomers to learn how to contribute to an open source project.

Prof. Schaeffer’s mini-magnetosphere project supported workforce development at the postdoctoral, graduate, and undergraduate levels. A postdoc was trained in all aspects of experimental design and data analysis, while a master’s student was trained on numerical simulations. A graduate student is currently being trained on experiments for this project. Four undergraduate students, including two women, were mentored as part of summer or independent research courses. This project is providing experience to a high school student as part of a collaboration with a local high school. Results from this project were highlighted for a broad public audience in AIP News and New Scientist.

4. Proposed Software Development Activities

We will now describe the major priorities in PlasmaPy’s software development roadmap that we will undertake in this effort.¹⁰ We will prioritize contributions based on community input and feedback, and support the broader community with their contributions to PlasmaPy and affiliated packages. All extensions to PlasmaPy’s capabilities will include documentation and tests, and most will include example Jupyter notebooks. Investigator responsibilities and the project timeline are included in the Management and Coordination Plan. Except in performance critical locations, functionality will be compatible with `astropy.units`. Throughout this project, we will support new users and contributors; advise students as described in the Mentoring Plan; hold weekly meetings and office hours; provide constructive code reviews; and partner with MagNetUS, PyHC, and the HEDP community.

¹⁰We do not include software development activities solely related to fusion energy sciences (FES) in this proposal because such tasks are traditionally funded by the Department of Energy rather than NSF. However, we will coordinate with members of the FES community on their contributions and include them in the educational activities described in §5.

4.1. Laboratory Plasma Diagnostics

We will enhance PlasmaPy's experimental analysis suite to provide the laboratory plasma physics community with additional, powerful tools for analyzing data from widely used diagnostics, thus streamlining research workflows and accelerating insights into experimental results. Laboratory diagnostics for magnetized plasmas are crucial for addressing fundamental questions in plasma science, including the study of plasma turbulence (Schaffner et al. 2012); magnetic reconnection (Yamada et al. 2010); magnetized collisionless shock formation (Niemann et al. 2014); the solar corona heating problem (Bose et al. 2024); and the auroral acceleration problem (Schroeder et al. 2021). Analyzing the data generated by, for example, magnetic probes (magnetic field time variation and topology), Thomson scattering (few-point electron density and temperature), laser-induced fluorescence (LIF; ion velocity distribution functions), and Langmuir probes (volumetric measurements of plasma potential, electron temperature and density) allows for precise measurements of plasma parameters, enabling the validation of theoretical models and numerical simulations. These tools are widespread and the analysis routines have been needlessly re-written by each new generation of graduate students in plasma science. By providing community validated analysis tools, we will reduce duplication of effort so that researchers can concentrate on the science instead. PlasmaPy provides the unique opportunity to develop robust diagnostic analysis tools, reviewed by a diverse community base and tested against a wide parameter space. This effort will provide better transfer of knowledge from one generation of scientists to the next and promote a faster and more consistent analysis cycle.

PlasmaPy will provide two flavors of analysis tools: (1) focused tools which reside in `plasmapy.analysis`, and (2) integrated tools which reside in `plasmapy.diagnostics`. Focused tools are well-defined, single-purpose functions that calculate a given parameter for a given diagnostic. These functions are designed around NumPy arrays and prioritize computational efficiency. Integrated tools are `xarray` accessors and expand upon the focused tools. `plasmapy.diagnostics` provides a more inclusive analysis environment that (1) collects all related diagnostic focused tools, (2) incorporates diagnostic metadata, (3) incorporates a centralized structure (`xarray.Dataset`) for data and metadata management, and (4) provides quick visualization tools.

Nearly all new incorporated plasma diagnostics will have functionality in both focused and integrated tools, with focused analysis tools being developed first. This approach will: (1) lower the workload barrier for development and inclusion of new plasma diagnostic tools, (2) provide an analysis workflow that includes standardized diagnostic metadata, and (3) provide options for a user's own personal workflow.

To date, we have prioritized focused analysis tools. In the next development cycle we will expand on those tools while implementing the integrated tools framework and populating functionality. **We will add analysis functionality and educational notebooks for the diagnostics most commonly used in laboratory plasma experiments: hairpin probes, Mach probes, magnetic flux probes, emissive probes, interferometry, and laser-induced fluorescence.** Any remaining time will be used to add spectroscopic diagnostics using functionality from `specutils` (an affiliated package of Astropy).

To enhance code usability we will focus on the continued implementation of an intuitive package structure, clean interfaces, and quick data visualization. An intuitive package structure increases discoverability of functionality. Clean interfaces are designed with explicitly named functionality and arguments, similarly named conceptual arguments across subpackages, and well-tailored arguments and functions that do singular tasks. Quick plotting routines will be implemented using `matplotlib` so analysis results can be visualized and interpreted early and frequently in the analysis process. Visualization tools will be developed for both focused and integrated analysis tools.

4.2. High Energy Density Physics

We propose to expand PlasmaPy to include 1) toolkits to collectively analyze data from most widely used HEDP diagnostics, and 2) educational resources such as Jupyter notebooks. PlasmaPy currently has modules for two critical HEDP diagnostics: optical Thomson scattering (OTS), which provides localized measurements of electron density & temperature, and charged particle radiography (CPR), which is the only practical means of measuring electromagnetic fields in high energy

density (HED) plasma. We propose to expand these modules by adding new HEDP diagnostic analysis capabilities along with associated educational materials.

We will expand PlasmaPy's OTS capabilities and allow fitting of the non-Maxwellian distributions that are common in HED plasma. The `thomson` module includes forward modeling and fitting of Thomson scattering spectra assuming Maxwellian velocity distributions. We will update this to include any user-supplied velocity distribution. We will update the OTS spectral fitting routine to allow reconstructions of plasma parameters from data collected from non-Maxwellian plasmas. As part of the fitting routine, we will explore adding new optimization algorithms beyond those currently included (e.g., automatic differentiation) that may be better suited to the large number of free parameters inherent in non-Maxwellian distributions. This will allow scientists to extract plasma parameters from a broader range of HED experiments, especially in kinetic-scale and collisionless regimes.

PlasmaPy's current CPR module is limited to forward modeling of synthetic images from supplied 3D electromagnetic field configurations. **We will expand the CPR module to add reconstruction algorithms that can take collected data (e.g., proton flux images) and return path-integrated electromagnetic field profiles.** Several models exist for reconstructions, from relatively simple ODE solvers for 1D reconstructions to more sophisticated Monge-Ampere algorithms for 2D reconstructions. We will implement at least one 1D and one 2D solver. Given the importance of measuring electromagnetic fields for a wide range of phenomena, such reconstructions are very common in HEDP.

We will add **refractive imaging** capabilities to PlasmaPy, including both **shadowgraphy** and **angular filter refractometry** (a variation of schlieren imaging). Refractive imaging measures 2D density profiles and is especially useful for measuring large density gradients such as those found in HED shock experiments. We will add both forward models and reconstruction algorithms for these diagnostics. We will add capabilities for **particle energy spectrometers** that utilize magnets to disperse particles in space based on their energy distribution. These are one of the primary ways to measure energetic particles in HED plasmas. We will add a module that will include routines for processing image plate data and calibrating the energy response of the spectrometer based on an input magnetic field profile.

The addition of these capabilities will help address forefront questions in HEDP science, especially within the field of laboratory astrophysics, where all of these diagnostics are commonly used. Phenomena such as collisionless shocks and magnetic reconnection are ubiquitous in astrophysical systems and can now be recreated in laboratory experiments; however, they often require a kinetic-scale description to address fundamental questions about how particles and fields interact, and so will benefit from the added OTS, CPR, and refractive imaging capabilities that allow scientists to analyse data in this regime. Likewise, these phenomena are associated with non-thermal particle distributions and particle acceleration that remain poorly understood theoretically, and so will benefit from new capabilities that allow analysis of particle spectrometer data of energetic particles. As we implement these capabilities, we will coordinate with the NSF Zetawatt-Equivalent Ultrashort pulse laser System (ZEUS), a recently-completed HED facility, via Prof. Kuranz. ZEUS is developing OTS, particle radiography, and refractive imaging diagnostics, so the expanded tools will allow ZEUS users to quickly process and analyze data while providing feedback for further module development in PlasmaPy.

We will concurrently develop educational notebooks that complement the existing and added HEDP capabilities. The notebooks will serve as learning aids for the functionality of these HEDP diagnostics, the physics behind them, and the science that can be done with them. For example, for the OTS module, we would develop notebooks that demonstrate how to forward model non-Maxwellian velocity distributions, derive the Thomson scattering cross section, and calculate jump conditions across a shock that was diagnosed with OTS in an experiment.

4.3. Interoperability with the Python environment for heliophysics

The mission of the **Python in Heliophysics Community** (PyHC) is to facilitate scientific discovery by promoting the use and development of sustainable open source software across the solar and space physics community. Because the Sun and heliosphere are plasma, PlasmaPy has been a core package of PyHC since 2019 (along with SunPy, SpacePy, pySPEDAS, pysat, Kamodo, and `fiasco`). Dr. Murphy has represented PlasmaPy in PyHC since 2018. The biggest challenge facing PyHC has been to foster

interoperability. This challenge is particularly difficult because most PyHC packages were developed independently and predate PyHC by several years. A few PyHC packages — including SunPy, PlasmaPy, and `fiasco` — are growing a pocket of interoperability by leveraging Astropy. We propose a series of tasks to improve interoperability between PlasmaPy and PyHC. Throughout this effort, we will communicate with PyHC package maintainers via biweekly virtual meetings and biannual workshops.

We will create `plasmapy.distribution` to host classes that describe analytical and discretized velocity distribution functions (VDFs). Particles in a plasma commonly follow a VDF that departs significantly from a Maxwellian. Non-Maxwellian VDFs in space, laboratory, and HED plasmas provide a window into a rich variety of collisionless plasma processes like wave-particle interactions, particle acceleration, shocks, reconnection, turbulence, energy transport and conversion, and microinstabilities. We will deprecate the `formulary` functions for kappa and Maxwellian VDFs in favor of classes in `plasmapy.distribution` for each type of distribution function. The `Maxwellian`, `BiMaxwellian`, and `KappaDistribution` classes will accept quantities such as temperature, bulk velocity, particle, and dimensionality as arguments. These classes will have methods for the VDF; cumulative distribution function; mean, most probable, and root mean square speeds; variance; skewness; excess kurtosis; and entropy. We will create a class for a discretized VDF with a similar API, along with methods to fit the distribution function to an analytical VDF, view pitch angle distributions (relative to the magnetic field), and determine stability. These classes will include visualization methods and educational docstrings. Finally, we will create a class to represent a time series of discretized distribution functions.

We will incorporate non-equilibrium ionization modeling capabilities from PlasmaPy-NEI into `fiasco`. Collaborator W. Barnes created `fiasco` (Barnes et al. 2024) to be a Pythonic interface to the CHIANTI atomic database, which is widely used by solar physicists to analyze spectra and model atomic processes. This package is interoperable with older capabilities from `plasmapy.particles`. We will work with Dr. Barnes to make `fiasco` interoperable with PlasmaPy's `ParticleList` and `IonizationState` data structures. When a plasma undergoes a rapid change in temperature, it takes some time for ionization and recombination reactions to bring the ionization state distribution back to equilibrium. If a hydrogen plasma starts off at 10^4 K with an ionization fraction of 1% and is instantaneously heated to 10 MK, then it could take minutes to hours for the plasma to become 100% ionized. In the meantime, the plasma is in non-equilibrium ionization (NEI). NEI effects must be modeled to accurately interpret in situ observations of the solar wind, and remote observations of both coronal mass ejections (CMEs) and supernova remnant shock waves. Using NEI forward modeling in conjunction with remote or in situ observations lets us constrain the thermal history of plasma (e.g., Murphy et al. 2011). PlasmaPy-NEI is an affiliated package that performs highly customizable NEI modeling of plasma, and has been used to constrain plasma heating in the solar wind and CMEs (DuPont et al. 2020, Wilson et al. 2023). However, PlasmaPy-NEI lacks functionality to predict spectral line emission. Incorporating PlasmaPy-NEI's modeling capabilities into `fiasco` will simplify the prediction of spectral line emission, and thus greatly reduce the difficulty of comparing the models to observations. This task will leverage `fiasco`'s existing capabilities and improve sustainability by reducing the overall maintenance burden.

We will add functionality to read spacecraft data into PlasmaPy data structures. Space missions such as *Solar Orbiter* and the *Advanced Composition Explorer* have instruments that directly measure the composition of the solar wind (i.e., the ionization states for different elements). We will create functionality to read composition data into `IonizationState` data structures that can be directly compared to the results of NEI modeling in `fiasco`. We will similarly create functionality to read VDF data into the new data structure for discretized distribution functions. We will prioritize missions with widely used data, and leverage an existing CDF file reader such as `cdflib` or `spacepy.pycdf`. If using the latter, we will explore the option of adding this functionality directly to SpacePy instead of including it in PlasmaPy.

4.4. Improving the data environment for plasma science

One of the most significant barriers to making plasma science open is its data environment (Murphy 2023c). While open access data sets are common in heliophysics and astronomy, very few data sets from laboratory plasma physics are openly available. Data sets are developed independently by each

facility and thus lack interoperability. For example, suppose we are performing similar experiments at two different facilities: BaPSF and WiPPL. Because the data sets were designed in isolation from each other, we have to learn multiple data formats and write separate software to perform the same analysis.

A metadata standard is an agreed-upon framework that dictates how metadata should be created, structured, and maintained. Metadata standardization is essential for making scientific data sets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR; Wilkinson et al. 2016). Metadata standards ensure that data sets are machine-readable and human-understandable. The data environment in fundamental plasma science is difficult to navigate because (1) few metadata standards exist, and (2) very few data sets follow a metadata standard. The lack of standardization inhibits innovation by making it harder to find relevant data sets, understand data sets acquired at other facilities, collaborate with other researchers, perform machine learning studies, and write general purpose scientific software.

In the last few years, open metadata standards have begun emerging in fundamental plasma science and HEDP. **OpenPMD** is a metadata standard that provides naming and attribute conventions for particle and mesh based data, in particular from PIC simulations.¹¹ OpenPMD has been adopted by at least 17 plasma simulation codes. **Plasma-MDS** is a metadata standard for research data in plasma science and technology (Franke et al. 2020). This schema describes how to include information about plasma source, medium, and target; plasma diagnostics; and simulation/modeling methods. Plasma-MDS has been adopted by several European projects (e.g., the Interdisciplinary Plasma Technology Data Platform), but has seen limited adoption in domestic plasma research. There are also specialized metadata standards such as **pradformat** for CPR data and metadata standards under active development such as the Helmholtz Laser-Plasma Metadata Initiative (**HELPMI**) for ultra-high intensity laser plasma experiments.

The plasma science community is now recognizing the importance of adopting open metadata standards, as judged by community reviews and reports (NASEM 2021, APS DPP CPP 2020, FESAC 2020, LaserNetUS 2023, Anirudh et al. 2022, Feister et al. 2023, Gruber et al. 2023) and even organizational bylaws (MagNetUS 2022). Despite this recognition, adoption of metadata standards at experimental plasma research facilities has been very limited. With the exception of openPMD, few software tools exist to read, validate, and write plasma data sets following these standards. It is therefore very difficult at present for facilities to adopt a metadata standard, and most lack the time and resources to attempt this.

We propose to implement and improve functionality in PlasmaPy to interact with plasma data sets that follow existing and emerging open metadata standards. PlasmaPy contains a `Plasma` factory class that was added by a former Google Summer of Code student. Like SunPy's core `Map` class, instantiation of `Plasma` will cause it to choose the appropriate subclass based on the contents and structure of the file provided to it (Leonard 2018). The original implementation contains a subclass for HDF5 files for the basic version of the openPMD standard. We will update the implementation of the openPMD subclass to include the six extensions to openPMD that have been added since the original implementation. When possible, we will leverage existing Python tools for working with openPMD files. We will add `Plasma` subclasses that contain a reader, validator, and writer for HDF5 files that follow each of the Plasma-MDS, pradformat, and HELPMI standards. As these metadata standards are implemented, we will place high interoperability with the `analysis`, `diagnostics`, `formulary`, and `plasma` subpackages, as well as `astropy.units`. Because metadata standards are independent of file format, we will implement back-ends for different file types such as netCDF and ADIOS as needed.

We will work with the MagNetUS community to improve its data environment. As the inaugural chair of the Data and Software Working Group, Dr. Murphy has built a working relationship with the people at most MagNetUS facilities who have responsibility for data management. We will request sample data sets from MagNetUS facilities including MPRL, PHASMA at West Virginia University, BaPSF, and the Bryn Mawr Plasma Laboratory. We will use the functionality described above to reorganize data files to follow

¹¹Particle-in-cell simulations are used to investigate the wide range of plasma phenomena that cannot be described with a fluid model, including shocks, magnetic reconnection, plasma wave propagation and interactions, turbulent heating in the solar wind, laser-plasma interactions, and instabilities.

Plasma-MDS.¹² We will request sample ZEUS data sets and convert them into the HELPMI standard with help from Prof. Kuranz and her colleagues. We will share the methods we used for standardizing data sets with each facility, and provide tutorials at MagNetUS meetings on how to use this functionality and best practices for stewardship of scientific data. This effort will ensure that the new functionality in PlasmaPy is user-friendly, well-documented, and well-tested. In the long-term, these activities will improve the combined software and data environments for fundamental plasma science to enable studies that make use of data from multiple facilities (including machine learning studies).

4.5. Package infrastructure

Regular maintenance is vital to the health of software. We will regularly perform maintenance and improve package infrastructure throughout this project. We will routinely update code, tests, and documentation after upstream packages have breaking changes and/or deprecations. Because the Python packaging landscape is continually changing, we will periodically update packaging infrastructure to improve contributor experience and be consistent with best practices. We will expand usage of type hint annotations with static type checking. We will implement new linters and code improvement tools as they become available and sufficiently mature, as appropriate. We will periodically refactor existing code to reduce cognitive complexity or mitigate performance bottlenecks. For sustainability, we will update the contributor guide to be consistent with current package, testing, and documentation infrastructure.

5. Proposed Research Software Engineering Training Activities

We will lead frequent tutorials on PlasmaPy, research software engineering, and open plasma science. We will provide tutorials on PlasmaPy at events such as the annual APS DPP meeting, MagNetUS meetings, PyHC summer schools, and the SULI introductory course. We will invite attendees to contribute to PlasmaPy. We will upload tutorial videos to YouTube. We will expand the tutorial notebooks into full lessons in the style of The Carpentries so that tutorials can be led by others. We will create intermediate & advanced tutorials for specific subpackages and diagnostics.

We will host three PlasmaPy Summer Schools. Having established and grown the PlasmaPy software ecosystem, we now propose to grow the contributor base to improve software sustainability and increase the rate at which plasma community members contribute functionality. Because it is quite rare for plasma coursework to cover how to write software, there is a significant need to provide the emerging generation of plasma scientists with opportunities to learn essential RSE skills. While we provided tutorials on these topics during our pandemic era virtual Plasma Hack Weeks, our experience during the first PlasmaPy Summer School demonstrated that **direct, interactive, in-person training is the most effective way to impart RSE skills.** We will invite applications through various plasma and fusion relevant networks (including CRANE), and accept 25 applicants to be provided with full travel funding. We will allow up to 10 more applicants to participate without travel support. To be held again at Bryn Mawr College, the school will provide an intensive curriculum on research software engineering skills and lessons on how to use existing modules in PlasmaPy. The curriculum will include lessons on version control with `git` and GitHub, writing clean code, software testing, how to write software documentation, the code contribution workflow, and how to perform constructive code reviews. Hands-on activities will include guided walkthroughs on making actual contributions to PlasmaPy. Lessons will be taught using Jupyter notebooks via Google Colab. Lessons will be guided by Dr. Murphy, Prof. Schaffner, and consultant Shauna Gordon-McKeon, who was brought in to run tutorials during the first school. Each day will include an opportunity for participants to interact with instructors, teaching assistants, and other participants through unconference sessions in addition to the lessons and walkthroughs. These summer schools will provide foundational knowledge needed by participants to contribute to open source scientific projects.

This project will support ≥ 15 years worth of opportunities for early career scientists to work directly with the proposal team on contributions to PlasmaPy. Every year of this project includes 12-month opportunities for a postbaccalaureate or predoctoral fellow to work with Dr. Murphy at SAO, and

¹²The Integrated Modeling & Analysis Suite (IMAS) for the International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) includes a closed access metadata standard used for magnetic confinement fusion devices. If this standard is made openly available, we will explore it as an alternative to Plasma-MDS.

for a postbaccalaureate to work with the UCLA team. We will provide an undergraduate student with a research opportunity to work with the UCLA team in each of years 2–5, and summer research opportunities for Bryn Mawr students to work with Prof. Schaffner. The UCLA participants will focus on laboratory plasma and HEDP diagnostics. SAO participants will work on projects related to heliophysics or fundamental plasma science such as distribution functions (§4.3), adding general dispersion relation solvers for plasma waves (e.g., Xie 2014, Xie & Xiao 2014, Verscharen & Chandran 2018), equilibrium and stability analysis (e.g., Bernstein et al. 1958, Tajima 2004), plasma turbulence analysis techniques (e.g., Fujisawa 2010), and magnetic topology visualization techniques (e.g., Haynes & Parnell 2007, 2010). The projects for predoctoral fellows will be selected to be closely related to their thesis research. As described in the Mentoring Plan, we will place high priority on providing opportunities for these participants to learn both essential RSE skills and plasma science.

This project will support the annual 16-week free online Python course run by the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE) for two cycles.¹³ CRANE is a non-profit led by graduate students, postdocs and other early-career scientists from historically marginalized groups who provide a series of weekly Python virtual seminars in the spring on computational physics geared towards undergraduate and graduate students from these underrepresented groups who have expressed interest in physics and astronomy. CRANE has run three annual cycles of the course with a fourth cycle starting in January 2025. Lessons are conducted via Zoom and utilize Google Colab. All course materials are developed by the early-career members of CRANE who serve as course instructors and teaching assistants. **The CRANE budget request includes funding to provide stipends to CRANE students and instructors during the workshop.** These stipends will compensate graduate students for their time teaching, writing, and editing notebooks. We will add lessons based on feedback from CRANE students and the project team members. Most of our target audience for CRANE are low income, first-generation college students from colleges with limited or no access to computational physics. Therefore, the program expects zero computational background from students. The stipends allow CRANE students to participate who otherwise may not be able to due to employment, childcare, or other commitments.

The CRANE curriculum teaches introductory Python, numerical methods, foundational computational skills, and advanced algorithms — all foundational skills needed for computational physics or astronomy research. The Introduction to Python section includes Boolean logic, loops, functions, and plotting. The numerical methods section includes the Euler Method, Runge-Kutta Method, Finite Difference Method, and built-in Python solvers to solve introductory mechanics and electromagnetism problems, such as projectile motion, pendulum motion, and the Lorentz Force. Since these problems have analytic solutions, CRANE shows how scientists approximate solutions using numerical methods. Just like how PlasmaPy uses numerical solvers to approximate solutions, the students learn how these numerical solvers work, so that they can use them in their future computational research equipped with an understanding of the underlying numerical methods. The foundational skills the students learn include using the Linux terminal with bash commands, collaborative project management using `git` and GitHub, and scientific writing with LaTeX. These skills are invaluable to students aspiring to perform computational research or physics software development.

All of these skills lead up to the advanced tracks in CRANE, which include PIC methods, Monte Carlo, machine learning, astronomy data analysis, magnetohydrodynamics with the code FLASH, and signal and image processing. These tracks run in parallel so students can take one or more of them. With this collaboration, PlasmaPy will bring plasma physics to a wider, more diverse audience by creating a PlasmaPy track and introducing computational plasma physics and data analysis using this tool. This will help recruit students whom the physics community has historically underserved into the field. The PlasmaPy RSE workforce development track will include writing effective documentation, creating software tests, and strategies for writing clean code. Some of these ideas are scattered throughout the

¹³This task addresses the following recommendation from the recent plasma decadal review (NASEM 2021): *“Federal agencies (e.g., DOE, NSF, NASA, DoD) should structure funding to support undergraduate and graduate educational, training, and research opportunities—including faculty—and encourage and enable access to plasmas physics for diverse populations.”*

existing CRANE workshops, but without a PlasmaPy track, there is presently no dedicated time for learning these technical professional development skills that transform beginner computationalists into high-quality organized researchers. Through this proposal, PlasmaPy aims to support this vital educational and workforce development activity and incorporate PlasmaPy elements into course modules. PlasmaPy is already incorporated in some CRANE modules, such as Langmuir probe analysis. Modules such as `plasmapy.formulary` and new HEDP capabilities would fit into a new CRANE PlasmaPy track since these are introductory plasma physics materials used across different subfields. With these skills, these students will be prepared to start a computational research project. One such opportunity would be with CRANE leads. CRANE leads propose taking on CRANE students as summer interns to provide an opportunity to work on computational research the following summer after completing the workshop in the spring. Since many of the members in CRANE work at premier institutions with access to top-tier computational resources, this will give the student a chance to build their computational skills in a supportive environment. Paid internships are crucial for retention in physics and astronomy, especially for those considering graduate school. **CRANE proposes to create a recurring 10 week summer internship for students who have completed the workshop.** Having the opportunity to present research at a conference would be an invaluable experience for the student. **We will also recruit current and former CRANE students for 1 year postbaccalaureate training opportunities at SAO and/or UCLA.** The chance to learn these skills and use them in a project would be invaluable for recruiting and retaining marginalized students while training the next generation of RSEs. Forging a partnership between CRANE and PlasmaPy will improve the sustainability of both efforts.

6. Broader Impacts

This project will lay a foundation for open and reproducible plasma science. Reproducibility is a cornerstone of the scientific method. Unfortunately, the scientific reproducibility best practices that are rapidly being adopted in fields like psychology and astrophysics have yet to be widely adopted in plasma physics (Murphy et al. 2019b, Murphy 2023c). The predominant closed science practices inhibit reproducibility by making it extremely hard for researchers to replicate results or to reconcile differences between experiments. PlasmaPy — or something like it — is necessary to make plasma research open and reproducible. Implementation of readers, validators, and writers for emerging plasma metadata standards is vital to making laboratory plasma data sets findable, accessible, interoperable, and reproducible (FAIR; Wilkinson et al. 2016). We are proposing to engage in a multi-year effort to grow the necessary software infrastructure to make plasma data sets FAIR in order to improve reproducibility, enhance discoverability, greatly reduce the difficulty of performing archival and machine learning projects that use data from multiple facilities, allow data to be used to its fullest potential, and enable innovation. An open source software ecosystem will improve the quality and efficiency of plasma research.

The PlasmaPy ecosystem allows the plasma community to pool resources and enhance collaborations within and across disciplines. Historically, each MagNetUS user facility has developed its own software stack to analyze experimental data, leading to significant duplication of effort and a severe lack of interoperability. Guest investigators at one facility have had to learn new software and data storage conventions if they are awarded time at a different facility. It has therefore been unnecessarily difficult to perform the same analysis on multiple experiments. A shared software ecosystem will reduce both costly duplication of effort and the difficulty of comparing results from different experiments. Similarly, experimentalists and spacecraft observers who study similar phenomena currently operate in quite distinct software environments, making comparisons between the two unnecessarily difficult. A unified software approach will save time and resources and foster more efficient and collaborative research within the plasma community. PlasmaPy reduces the need to rewrite functionality that already exists but is hard to read, inadequately documented, or closed source. Researchers that reuse existing code will not have to spend time rewriting what has already been written. This broader impact will be fully realized by training the next generation of RSEs in plasma science via the educational activities described above.

Growing the PlasmaPy ecosystem will reduce barriers to entry and broaden access to plasma research and education. Realizing the full potential of this ecosystem will ensure that students can get

off to a fast start for their first research projects. Continued growth and adoption of PlasmaPy will enable students and scientists at small or under-resourced institutions to not only have the same access to plasma research software as flagship institutions, but also contribute to it. PlasmaPy is already allowing undergraduates to learn common analysis techniques for plasma research such as Langmuir analysis (A. Murphy et al. 2023, L. Murphy 2024, Creamer 2024) and even perform innovative machine learning studies (Eisenbach et al. 2025). Our continued work will provide researchers at small schools with access to cutting-edge research tools developed in collaboration with scientists at major plasma institutions.

Expanding PlasmaPy functionality will reduce the software development burden needed to establish small-scale experiments. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of plasma laboratories developed outside flagship institutions. The Small College Plasma Consortium (SCPC) is a coalition of small, predominantly undergraduate, and liberal arts colleges with faculty who conduct plasma research. Since faculty at these schools interface mostly with undergraduate students, supporting plasma education at these locations is particularly impactful for workforce development. When building a small-scale plasma experiment, a time-consuming but often overlooked task is to create the software needed to analyze the results. Continued growth of PlasmaPy will substantially reduce the software development overhead while providing undergraduate researchers with access to well-documented code and multiple example notebooks. This benefit will be greatest at small institutions and institutions with limited resources, such as members of the SCPC.

PlasmaPy is growing into an important freely available educational resource for plasma science. PlasmaPy docstrings not only describe how to use a function or class, but also the underlying physics. In some cases, `formulary` docstrings have information that is currently missing from Wikipedia (such as for the Buchsbaum frequency). The docstrings are supplemented by a gallery of 31 example Jupyter notebooks which use PlasmaPy to introduce plasma concepts and analysis techniques. We will expand the gallery to include a systematic progression of notebooks for use in introductory physics and plasma courses.¹⁴ We will partner with educators in the plasma community who will use the notebooks in actual courses, including in CRANE and the SCPC. We will connect to other fields by adding lessons to Learn Astropy and the PyHC gallery.

We will build a foundation of psychological safety to encourage growth of the PlasmaPy community by making it a welcoming space for new contributors. Psychological safety is the shared belief that a workplace is safe for interpersonal risk taking (Edmondson 2018, Clark 2020), and is sometimes referred to as “permission for candor.” Without psychological safety, team members will not speak up with concerns or new ideas for fear of being punished. With psychological safety, team members will feel able to risk bringing up new and innovative ideas. A two-year study by Google found that psychological safety was the most important factor in determining team performance (Duhigg 2016). Psychological safety is foundational not only to open science but also diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility (Young-McLear et al. 2021). Psychological safety is a particularly important evidence-based practice for this proposal because of the need for software sustainability and community growth, and the need to focus on human as well as technical aspects of cyberinfrastructure. Dr. Murphy previously co-organized three virtual community workshops on psychological safety that were funded through APS DPP, and expects to co-organize more in the future. We will invite the PlasmaPy community to attend these workshops. We will apply lessons from these workshops as code review best practices to make sure new contributors feel safe to potentially make mistakes on their way to becoming experienced contributors. Our tutorial and summer school activities will incorporate psychological safety practices as well. By establishing psychological safety within our PlasmaPy project ecosystem, we will encourage expansion of these practices throughout the plasma community and beyond.

¹⁴This task addresses the following recommendation from the recent plasma decadal review (NASEM 2021): *“Computational plasma science and engineering, supported by NSF, should include projects for writing textbooks and developing courses to train the current and next generation of computational plasma scientists, and to enable noncomputer experts to make optimal use of computations.”*

Management and Coordination Plan

Team Member Roles and Responsibilities

Dr. Nicholas Murphy (PI: SAO) will coordinate the activities described in this proposal, monitor progress of project deliverables, guide the overall direction of the PlasmaPy project, advise and mentor postbaccalaureate and predoctoral fellows at SAO, provide user support, organize weekly meetings, hold weekly virtual office hours, lead workshops and tutorials, perform constructive code reviews, serve on PlasmaPy's coordinating committee, act as the point of contact with the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC), and engage with the broader plasma community. Dr. Murphy will lead the development of PlasmaPy's `particles`, `distribution`, `formulary`, and `plasma` subpackages; and perform or oversee software development tasks related to heliophysics, fundamental plasma science, and improvements to the data environment for plasma science. Dr. Murphy will have primary responsibility for maintaining and improving package infrastructure (including continuous integration testing, documentation, and automating releases) and PlasmaPy's Contributor Guide, and will co-develop educational materials bridging PlasmaPy and CRANE.

Prof. David Schaffner (PI: Bryn Mawr College) will lead the organization of the PlasmaPy Summer School in 2026, 2028, and 2030. He will oversee the educational endeavors of the project, including development of tutorial notebooks for use in plasma courses. He will serve as the primary administrator for participant travel support, website needs, and exhibitor needs for the annual American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP) meeting. He will serve as a point of contact between PlasmaPy and CRANE, and be responsible for engaging with the Small College Plasma Consortium.

Sara Negussie (PI: CRANE) serves as a board member of CRANE, where she leads, TAs, and develops some of the lessons in the curriculum for the 16-week Python workshop, which is geared towards undergraduates who come from underrepresented backgrounds and are interested in plasma physics. She will serve as a point of contact between CRANE and PlasmaPy. She will coordinate with PlasmaPy to help recruit interns from CRANE to serve as year-long postbacs at either SAO or UCLA.

Dr. Stephen Vincena (PI: UCLA) will guide the overall activities of the project at UCLA, coordinate UCLA's activities with the PIs at collaborating institutions, assist in the development of `plasmapy.diagnostics`, provide technical expertise about plasma diagnostics, and co-advise undergraduates and postbacs at UCLA.

Dr. Erik Everson (Co-PI: UCLA) will lead the development of the PlasmaPy's `analysis`, `diagnostics`, and `dispersion` subpackages. Dr. Everson will perform or oversee code development tasks for laboratory plasma diagnostics and high energy density physics. Dr. Everson will share responsibility with Dr. Murphy for user support, holding office hours, performing code reviews, performing releases, serving on PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee, and package maintenance.

Prof. Derek Schaeffer (Co-PI: UCLA) will oversee the development of high energy density physics (HEDP) functionality in the `diagnostics` and `analysis` subpackages with Dr. Everson. He will co-advise students and postbacs at UCLA on HEDP projects, and coordinate with MagNetUS and ZEUS.

Dr. Peter Heuer (collaborator) is an experimental plasma physicist at the Laboratory for Laser Energetics at the University of Rochester and a frequent contributor to PlasmaPy. As the original author of the `charged_particle_radiography` and `thomson` modules in `plasmapy.diagnostics`, Dr. Heuer will share expertise on these modules and other HEDP diagnostics, and provide code reviews.

Prof. Carolyn Kuranz (collaborator) a Co-PI of the NSF Zetawatt-Equivalent Ultrashort pulse Laser System (ZEUS) at the University of Michigan. She will coordinate linkages between PlasmaPy and ZEUS and share expertise on HEDP diagnostics.

Dr. Will Barnes (collaborator) is a Research Assistant Professor at American University and the Deputy Lead Developer of SunPy. Dr. Barnes is the original creator of the `fiasco` package: a Pythonic interface to the CHIANTI atomic database which is widely used in solar physics. Dr. Barnes will share technical knowledge on `fiasco` and CHIANTI, collaborate on a roadmap for PlasmaPy/`fiasco` integration, and review the code contributions to `fiasco` to be made during this project.

Shauna Gordon-McKeon (paid consultant) is an open source software consultant, governance expert, and trainer with 14 years of experience. She co-organized the inaugural PlasmaPy Summer School and led multiple interactive trainings there on how to contribute to open source Python packages like PlasmaPy. She is expected to fill this role at the PlasmaPy Summer Schools in 2026, 2028, & 2030.

The responsibilities are broken down in the following Gantt chart:

We propose ~1.25 years for each major HEDP capability: OTS for non-Maxwellian distributions; CPR reconstruction techniques; refractive imaging; and particle energy spectrometers. Approximately three months of each of these major components will be dedicated to developing educational notebooks. The plasma diagnostic series includes functionality for analyzing data from: hairpin probes, Mach probes, magnetic flux probes, emissive probes, interferometry, and laser-induced fluorescence. Any remaining time will be used to implement spectroscopic diagnostics. Data environment tasks include revamping software infrastructure for the Plasma class; implementing functionality to interact with data sets from the openPMD, Plasma-MDS, HELPMI, and pradformat; applying these tools to actual data sets; and writing necessary documentation. If CRANE receives three years funding from a pending proposal to the Department of Energy, then the CRANE cycles supported through the proposed activities will be shifted to years 4 & 5.

PlasmaPy Governance

The defining documents for the PlasmaPy project are **PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals (PLEPs)**. A **standard PLEP** introduces and describes a major change to the PlasmaPy code base, such as a new feature or subpackage, major refactoring of an existing subpackage, or a major backwards incompatible change. A standard PLEP will start out as a proposal and eventually evolve into a design document if accepted. A **process PLEP** describes a new process or change to an existing process in the management and coordination of PlasmaPy. Examples include changes to PlasmaPy decision-making processes or management structure, guidelines, or procedures. Accepted process PLEPs describe the governance of PlasmaPy. An **informational PLEP** provides information to the broader PlasmaPy community. PLEPs are openly archived on Zenodo. The purposes and guidelines of PLEPs are defined in PLEP 1. PLEPs provide an opportunity for all members of the plasma community to help guide the direction of PlasmaPy and affiliated packages. Similarly, PyHC recently began PyHC Enhancement Proposals (PHEPs). The PHEP process will be used for major code development activities involving interoperability between PlasmaPy and PyHC packages.

PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee oversees and manages project activities. The responsibilities of the Coordinating Committee are described in PLEP 2, and are to ensure that necessary roles are being filled, coordinate and delegate tasks, facilitate community-wide communication, oversee code development, manage the PlasmaPy repositories, regulate intercompatibility, seek funding mechanisms, coordinate grant proposals, facilitate compromises and cooperation, enforce the code of conduct, and foster a culture of appreciation. The Coordinating Committee is responsible for making major decisions and official decisions on PLEPs after a period of community input and discussion. Day-to-day decisions on code development and community events do not go through the Coordinating Committee, and are instead made after informal discussions via our weekly meetings or on GitHub. The PlasmaPy community abides by version 2.1 of the Contributor Covenant Code of Conduct, which describes behaviors that contribute to a positive environment, unacceptable behaviors, the enforcement mechanism, and consequences of violations.

Coordination Mechanisms

PlasmaPy organizes several weekly virtual events to facilitate code development and coordinate activities across different institutions. These include a community code development meeting, a project coordination meeting, and virtual office hours offering the broader plasma community a chance to interact with PlasmaPy maintainers. Details about these meetings are on PlasmaPy's website. Informal day-to-day communication is done using Element: an open source messaging client. Community-wide updates will be disseminated periodically through a newsletter sent to the PlasmaPy email list. We will continue to use GitHub issues, pull requests, discussions, and projects for code development and roadmapping. We will create working groups to focus on topics such as education, diagnostics, and wave dispersion relations. The partnership between CRANE and PlasmaPy will be coordinated during the education working group meetings. The code contribution workflow is described in the Contributor Guide in PlasmaPy's online documentation.

Code development activities will be organized primarily using GitHub issues, pull requests, and discussions. We will continue to utilize GitHub Projects for management, enabling a unified approach within PlasmaPy's GitHub organization. This approach facilitates the centralization of code development and planning by interlinking tasks, such as issues and pull requests, across all PlasmaPy repositories. In this unified workspace, we will manage not only code development but also workshops, educational materials, and outreach activities, ensuring cohesive and streamlined project progression. Major proposed changes like the creation of a subpackage will be done via creation of a PLEP.

For each project to be performed by an undergraduate, postbac, or predoc, senior members of the team will create a GitHub issue with a detailed description of their project before they arrive. These issues will include physics background, helpful hints, implementation plans, and links to important references.

CRANE leadership meets weekly to discuss CRANE activities. Those outside of leadership, including PlasmaPy team members, will join these meetings to discuss partnership activities, when needed. Through these meetings, CRANE and PlasmaPy team members will work together to develop new advanced PlasmaPy tracks (including on Plasma subpackages and research software engineering skills)

Meetings and Workshops

As discussed in the Project Description, we will hold PlasmaPy Summer Schools in 2026, 2028, & 2030 to provide members of the broader plasma community with an opportunity to learn how to contribute to PlasmaPy. These summer schools will provide students, scientists, and faculty with an opportunity to learn important research software engineering skills that are usually not covered in physics coursework while growing PlasmaPy's contributor base. The budget for Bryn Mawr College includes full travel support for 25 participants at each of these summer schools to enable broader participation.

All members of the proposal team are planning to attend the annual meeting of the APS DPP in each year of the project. We will continue to reserve an exhibitor booth at each APS DPP meeting to demonstrate PlasmaPy, answer questions, receive community feedback, and provide in-person support to users. We expect to propose one or more mini-conferences or town halls on open source plasma software and/or open plasma science at some of the APS DPP meetings, along with PlasmaPy tutorials.

Data Management and Sharing Plan

Research products

The main research products of this project will be the **code, documentation,¹ and tests of PlasmaPy and affiliated packages**. We will also create research products, including **presentations, articles, tutorials**, and the **project website.²** We may also use **data sets** for tutorials, testing, calibration, and functionality needed by users (e.g., atomic data). PlasmaPy research products will continue to be released under permissive open source licenses to maximize the potential for use, modification, dissemination, and scientific reproducibility.

Licensing

PlasmaPy is developed openly on GitHub³ under the **BSD 3-clause license**. This license is permissive and does not restrict redistribution or modification. In contrast to copyleft licenses, the BSD 3-clause license permits relicensing and allows proprietary derivative works. Software released under the BSD 3-clause license may be combined with code released under other permissive open source licenses, copyleft licenses, and proprietary licenses. The BSD 3-clause license is also used by Astropy, SunPy, and fiasco (which are also developed on GitHub).

Publications, presentations, notebooks, and other research products associated with PlasmaPy will generally be made openly available under Creative Commons licenses. We will use the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license** for these research products. The CC BY 4.0 license allows redistribution and modification of the research product if attribution is provided. The attribution requirement ensures that provenance information will be made available for derivative works.

In rare situations, we may release research products under other licenses. For example, if a research product incorporates material that is licensed under a copyleft license (such as the GNU General Public License or the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License; CC BY-SA 4.0), then the resulting research product will be released under the license of the incorporated work. In other situations, we may release research products under the Creative Commons Universal Public Domain Dedication (CC0 1.0).

The licenses for the metadata standards to be implemented are CC BY 4.0 for Plasma-MDS and openPMD, CC BY-SA 4.0 for HELPMI, and the MIT license for pradformat. These standards are developed openly on GitHub with releases typically made available on Zenodo.

Notebooks added to Learn Astropy⁴ and the Python in Heliophysics Community gallery⁵ will be under the BSD 3-clause and MIT license, respectively.

¹ PlasmaPy's online documentation: <https://docs.plasmapy.org>

² PlasmaPy project website: <https://www.plasmapy.org>

³ PlasmaPy GitHub repository: <https://github.com/PlasmaPy/PlasmaPy>

⁴ Learn Astropy: <https://learn.astropy.org/>

⁵ The PyHC example gallery is available under the Examples tab from: <https://pyhc.org>

Versioning

PlasmaPy uses calendar versioning of the form `YYYY.M.PATCH`, where `YYYY` represents the year of the release, `M` represents the month of the original release, and `PATCH` represents the patch or bugfix number. For example, `v2024.10.0` was the first release of PlasmaPy in October of 2024. The motivation for PlasmaPy's calendar versioning policy is described in PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposal 8.

Availability

PlasmaPy is developed openly on GitHub. Anyone with access to GitHub can view and search through the entire code development history of the project (including all 935 issues and 1943 pull requests available at the time of writing).

The PlasmaPy organization on GitHub has public repositories for tutorials, PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals (PLEPs), the PlasmaPy project website, the Plasma Hack Week website, the PlasmaPy Summer School, non-equilibrium ionization (NEI) modeling functionality, and the PlasmaPy logo.

PlasmaPy releases are made available on the Python Package Index (PyPI) and conda-forge. The releases are also available on GitHub, and are uploaded to the PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo⁶ so that each release has a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) as its persistent identifier. The release process is described as part of our Delivery Mechanism and Community Usage Metrics.

We will continue openly uploading presentations, community papers, PLEPs, technical reports, and other research products to the PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo. Videos will be made available on YouTube and/or Zenodo.

⁶ PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/plasmapy>

Mentoring Plan

This project includes support for graduate students who will participate in the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO) Predoctoral Program in years 2 & 4. This program provides opportunities for graduate students from other universities to carry out doctoral research at the Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian (CfA) as Predoctoral Fellows (predocs) under the guidance of SAO scientists. When applicable, we will apply this mentoring plan for SAO postbaccalaureate participants (postbacs) in years 1, 3, & 5 and for undergraduates and postbacs at UCLA and Bryn Mawr College.

Each participant will be responsible for learning and performing research software engineering (RSE) activities for PlasmaPy. Predocs will add functionality directly related to their thesis research. SAO predocs and postbacs will be in cohorts of roughly twenty people, and have opportunities to participate in multiple professional development opportunities at the CfA each month. SAO participants will become members of the solar physics group at the CfA. We will recruit participants who are particularly interested in becoming RSEs, in particular from the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE).

Upon arrival, each participant will attend an **orientation session** to become acclimated to the institution and project. They will then have an in-depth discussion with their new advisor about potential areas of learning and growth in the next year, overarching career goals, specific objectives, and professional development opportunities. They will collaborate and agree upon an action plan — for both student and advisor — that will be periodically revisited. While each participant will have a local advisor who they will meet with ~1–3 times per week, all proposal team members will participate in their mentorship.

We will work to provide a healthy **culture & climate**. We will begin by creating a foundation of psychological safety (Edmondson 2018, Young-McLear et al. 2019) in four steps (Clark 2020): authenticity safety, learner safety, contributor safety, and finally challenger safety. For example, we will encourage participants to challenge the status quo by asking how they would change the onboarding process, thanking them for their feedback, and working with them to enact those changes. We will learn from and share resources on how to perform code reviews while ensuring psychological safety.

Because plasma courses rarely cover RSE skills, the **onboarding** process will emphasize developing the skills for contributing to open source projects like PlasmaPy via one-on-one tutorials with senior members of the team. All will have access to PlasmaPy's extensive Contributor Guide which covers the code contribution workflow, coding conventions & best practices, software testing, and writing documentation. Participants will make pull requests of gradually increasing complexity to explore different aspects of PlasmaPy (i.e., documentation, tests, & package infrastructure). They will have opportunities for pair programming with senior members of the team. Because most of the planned projects require some knowledge of plasma science, senior members of the team will engage in multiple one-on-one discussions to introduce the plasma physics behind each project.

We will encourage participants to engage in **professional development** activities related to their educational and career goals. Participants will be able to attend conferences (such as the annual meeting of the APS Division of Plasma Physics) and summer schools (such as the PlasmaPy Summer School and the Python in Heliophysics Community Summer School) related to their interests. We will introduce the participants to our colleagues in the field at these events to ensure sufficient **networking opportunities**.

We will provide opportunities for participants to learn **teaching and mentoring skills**. We will encourage them to attend mentoring workshops held at each institution, and become certified as instructors for Software Carpentry. We will invite participants to co-lead live coding tutorials for PlasmaPy, and encourage predocs to participate in CRANE as a lecturer, teaching assistant, and/or mentor.

We will provide the participants with **leadership opportunities**. We will ask each participant to join PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee so they can guide the future of the project. Participants will have the option to join or lead a working group for PlasmaPy and become a maintainer of a subpackage. We will encourage them to establish collaborations, organize events, develop tutorials, and present their work. We will continue to be available to provide mentorship even after they successfully complete their project.

Delivery Mechanism and Community Usage Metrics

Deliverables

The primarily ongoing deliverables of this project are **quarterly releases of PlasmaPy** with associated **documentation** and **tests**. Additional ongoing deliverables include **tutorials**, **guides**, **presentations**, **technical reports**, and **journal articles**. For testing or documentation purposes, some **data sets** may be created or compiled. The primary services to be rendered are **user support**, **contributor support**, and **tutorials** on how to use and/or contribute to PlasmaPy and affiliated packages.

Specific software deliverables include: diagnostic functionality to analyze data from hairpin probes, Mach probes, magnetic flux probes, emissive probes, interferometry, and laser-induced fluorescence; improved Thomson scattering fitting capabilities; reconstruction algorithms for charged particle radiography; refractive imaging analysis capabilities (including shadowgraphy and angular filter refractometry); analysis of particle energy spectrometer data; functionality to read, validate, and write plasma data sets that follow the Plasma-MDS, openPMD, pradformat, and HELPMI metadata standards; classes to study analytical and discretized velocity dispersion functions in laboratory & space plasmas; non-equilibrium ionization modeling capabilities in fiasco; functionality to read in space plasma data sets into PlasmaPy data structures; magnetic topology visualization functionality; and plasma equilibrium/stability analysis tools. All functionality will have tests and documentation, often in the form of example Jupyter notebooks.

Specific events include: PlasmaPy Summer Schools in each of 2026, 2028, & 2030; two cycles of the Computational Research Access Network (CRANE); ~4–8 PlasmaPy tutorials per year at different conferences; and weekly virtual PlasmaPy office hours.

Delivery mechanisms

Official releases of PlasmaPy will continue to be made available on the Python Package Index (PyPI) for installation using `pip` or `uv`, and `conda-forge` for installation with `conda`.

PlasmaPy has a GitHub workflow that can be triggered to create an issue containing the instructions and checklist for each release. The release checklist includes preliminary code quality updates, running regular and comprehensive tests, creating the actual release, and post-release tasks (such as updating the checklist). The release process itself is mostly automated and takes only a few minutes. When a release is created on GitHub, it triggers a GitHub workflow that uploads the release to the Python Package Index (PyPI). A release on PyPI triggers a pull request (PR) to the `conda-forge` feedstock. Once this PR is merged, the release becomes available via `conda-forge`. The release is uploaded to the *PlasmaPy Community* on Zenodo¹ and assigned the pre-reserved Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

PlasmaPy's online documentation² is hosted by Read the Docs. This includes the documentation for the stable release, past releases, and the latest version available on GitHub.

Research articles will be published in open access journals like the *Journal of Plasma Physics* or with an open access option. Tutorials, guides, presentations, PLEPs, technical reports, and data sets will all be accessible on GitHub, Zenodo, and/or PlasmaPy's online documentation.

Metrics

We will perform an annual survey of PlasmaPy's user and contributor communities for our primary usage metric. This survey will inquire about the frequency of PlasmaPy usage, preferred subpackages, how they learned about PlasmaPy, desired features, and the quality of their experiences contributing to the project. We will disseminate the survey through PlasmaPy's email newsletter, other

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/plasmapy>

² <https://docs.plasmapy.org>

communication channels, and various plasma community forums and newsletters. Our target is to achieve a 25% annual increase in the number of users as determined by the survey results.

We will use NASA's Astrophysics Data System (ADS) to keep track of papers that cite or acknowledge usage of PlasmaPy in physics, astronomy, and space science literature. These papers will be added to a dedicated bibliography in PlasmaPy's online documentation. Because authors of plasma research articles are less likely to cite software than authors in astronomical journals, PlasmaPy's documentation includes clear instructions on how to cite and acknowledge PlasmaPy to increase the completeness of this metric.

We will use monthly download statistics from PyPI and `conda-forge` (when available) as a proxy to gauge relative trends in PlasmaPy usage.

Readily available statistics from GitHub will help us assess usage, community interest, code development effectiveness, and the health and vitality of PlasmaPy's contributor base. Specific metrics include the number of issues raised or resolved; PRs created or merged; lines of code changed; the number of stars and forks of the repository; the total number of contributors; and the total number of unique contributors for each quarterly release. Our target is to increase the mean number of unique contributors per release by 20% each year.

We will qualitatively assess development by determining whether the most pressing capabilities are being created, bugs are being fixed, documentation is being written and maintained, pull requests are promptly being reviewed, new code is readable and maintainable, and the test suite is thorough and meets code quality standards.

We will perform program assessments for each PlasmaPy summer school and CRANE cycle to gauge the effectiveness and quality of the program.

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